

The charter is the foundational document that describes the rationale, goals, plan of work, resources needed, terms and conditions, and outcomes of a Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) project. Charters are written by core members of a project team in a series of planning meetings taking place over the course of a month. The planning process is intensive, collaborative and requires substantial input from everyone on a team. Charters serve as formalized agreements among all team members on such crucial questions as scope, technical design, infrastructural needs, and success criteria.

A draft of each project charter is peer-reviewed by all CDH staff, and optionally by additional partners or stakeholders, at a “design review” before the start of project work. It is circulated at least one week before the review takes place in an open comment period. Questions and concerns from this period may be raised at the design review. Project teams have two weeks after the design review to address any issues raised and make any requested changes. Project work only begins (and funds are released) once the charter has been finalized and signed by the Project Director (PI) and the CDH Faculty Director. Charters are amended as necessary throughout the project lifecycle to document major changes and note when “Built by CDH” Software Warranty and “Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement take effect, and serve as part of the CDH project archive.

CDH charters and their planning documents exist in several forms as we have refined them over the years and tailored them to the several types of projects we have supported. For more about CDH project management, including the charter process, visit: <https://cdh.princeton.edu/research/project-management/>

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CDH Project Charter - Princeton Prosody Archive 2017-18

Part I: Project Summary

1. Project Description & Objectives

The Princeton Prosody Archive (PPA) is a full-text searchable database of more than 5,000 digitized works on prosody published between 1570 and 1923, the only resource of its kind. Active since 2007, the PPA will use CDH resources for the 2017-2018 project cycle in order to overhaul the user interface and backend data structure so that we can publicly launch the Archive to scholars and researchers.

“Rebuilding the Archive and User Interface,” the proposed project for the 2017-2018 CDH grant cycle, picks up from the editorial curation and metadata cleaning completed during previous project cycles. It has the following objectives:

- **Articulate site layout and functionality.** This includes building detailed front end and administrative user stories; wireframing desired site functionality and layout; meeting with Technical Lead Rebecca Koeser and User Experience Designer Xinyi Li to discuss desired functionality and user experience; and fine-tuning user stories and wireframing after feedback.
- **Develop beta-site.** This includes running Solr instance on Archive (including excerpting 494 articles or chapters from larger volume); implementing full-text and metadata search; incorporating search visualizations (such as frequency of returned results over time); implementing desired administrative functionality; and holding bi-weekly check-ins to problem solve and answer questions.
- **Design test plan for beta-site.** This includes working with OIT user experience team once we have beta-site wireframe and designing user testing exercises.
- **Run usability testing on the beta-site.** This includes inviting select users from the Bain Swiggett Committee, Historical Poetics Group, and Poetry Graduate Colloquium to test site; reporting feedback to Technical Lead Rebecca Koeser and User Experience Designer Xinyi Li.
- **Document the new site and build repository of Archive for visiting scholars.** This includes beginning the write-up of site architecture on GitHub; documenting detailed workflow and instructions for PPA staff to follow when adding new works to the Archive; creating a questionnaire and repository for visiting scholars who want to analyze the Archive; and documenting how to access this repository for PPA staff to follow and instruct.
- **Enhance site functionality and user experience.** This includes implementing changes from testing groups and consulting with visualization developers such as Ben Schmidt from Bookworm.
- **Host PPA Advisory Board to test site.** This includes inviting the Advisory Board to the CDH to test new site; designing testing activities tailored for Board; and asking for feedback (technical and editorial).
- **Launch and publicize completed PPA.** This includes reviewing Board feedback; submitting to NINES for peer review; publicizing site through appropriate online channels; and submitting press release to major scholarly organizations.

2. Statement of Significance and Innovation

The PPA is the only large-scale corpus focused on the study of poetry and prosody in the English language. It aims to consolidate and collect prosodic materials in English into one searchable archive. This includes grammar handbooks, poetic treatises, versification manuals, elocution guides, editorial introductions, phonetic tracts, and journal articles pertaining to the measure and pronunciation of poetry. These texts tell us about the development of the study of poetics in linguistic science, in the study of phonology, and in the history of English literature prior to its institutionalization in the late nineteenth-century as a university discipline. Critical attention to these prosodic histories and debates is part of an emerging field in literary studies known as historical poetics.

3. Audience

The PPA's audience is scholars in historical poetics, history of linguistics, prosody, and versification; teachers who instruct on the evolution of poetic forms and genres; and computer scientists and digital humanists who wish to run textual analytic algorithms on a curated data set.

4. Project team

Project Director: Meredith Martin

Project Manager and Content Editor: Meagan Wilson (F17, S18) and Mary Naydan (S18)

Technical Lead: Rebecca Koeser

User Experience Designer: Xinyi Li

User Experience Consultant: Charles Kreitzberg

Project Designer: Rebecca Munson

Developer: Benjamin Hicks

Front-end Developer: TBD

Data Visualization Consultant: Jean Bauer

Database Design Consultant: Jean Bauer

Event Planning Consultant: Sarah Meadows

5. Main project outcomes (deliverables, products).

“Rebuilding the Archive and User Interface” has the following project deliverables:

- A developed and documented code base, including write-up on the data structure for the 5,000+ (494 of which are chapters or journal articles that must be excerpted from longer volumes) works currently in the PPA, including a new Solr instance.
- A completed user interface that enables scholars to access PPA materials through faceted search, published editorial content, and exportable bibliographies.
- Administrative functionality that enables project team members to: manage the volumes in the Archive, including adding and removing materials; run basic reports on Archive metadata; report and correct metadata and bibliographic errors; group different printings/editions of the same work in the Archive in order that users might access different versions; publish editorial material and project updates.

- A protocol and email address (not tied to a single person’s account) for managing comments and questions from researchers concerning missing works in the Archive and/or metadata errors.
- An on-site Archive repository with: a preparatory questionnaire asking scholars what type of data they would like to access and about their research goals; and directions for how visitors can then access the PPA’s full-text and metadata so that scholars who visit the CDH can use the Archive for their own research, textual analysis tools, algorithms, etc.

Out of scope for this project grant cycle are more sophisticated site features such as individual user accounts that enable scholars to build and share their own sub-collections on the site and comparative reading tools such as Juxta, which allows users to discern the differences between volumes of the same work. Also out of scope are non-HathiTrust works (including non-HathiTrust works cited in Brogan) and post-1923 publications.

6. Content and functionality

- ***What types of content or material will you be working with in this project?*** The PPA uses HathiTrust-digitized content, delivered to us via Princeton’s partnership with the HathiTrust Digital Library. All works are within fair use: published prior to 1923.
- ***What types of data or content will be generated as part of the research process for inclusion in the project deliverable?*** The project will generate GitHub repositories documenting the PPA’s data structure and site architecture; code for the new web site; a new Solr instance; and editorial blog posts.
- ***How will project team members need to interact with the content?*** Team members will need to access administrative functions (especially project manager and director) as well as the user interface during testing periods. Before the new site goes live, we will need the previous version to remain hosted in order to access PPA materials.
- ***How will the intended audience interact with the content?*** Test-groups, PPA Board testers, and finally the intended audience including those who want to work with the data on-site will interact with the PPA’s content through the new website during its various phases of development.

7. Resource needs

The PPA requests CDH staff time to develop the data structure, user interface, and on-site Archive repository for visiting scholars. We also request financial assistance given the included project budget.

8. Risks

Integrating non-Hathi material is our biggest risk; the system is designed dependent upon Hathi’s API. Fundamental changes to the Hathi API could negatively affect the site’s functionality. We will, however, always have the Pairtree data as a backup.

9. Interdependencies

The PPA depends upon the HathiTrust Digital Library, including the data structure of the Pairtree files utilized by HathiTrust for volume handoff to the PPA.

10. Project change process

Any significant changes (such as scope, timeline, work plan, budget, etc.) must be discussed and approved by the PI and the CDH Associate Director. These changes will be recorded and appended to the Project Charter. The CDH Advisor will assure that an amendment is completed within a two-week time-frame.

11. Rights and permissions

We will license under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). As an open source project, will license the code under Apache 2.0. We will fill out an invention disclosure form in order to gain approval from the Office of Technology Licensing in order to release the code. Before approval is granted, the code will be owned by the Trustees of Princeton University.

12. Data security considerations

The PPA will be hosted on OIT servers. The site provides full-text search and page image display for all users who can access HathiTrust. Onsite visitors can access the raw data.

13. Data management plan

The type of data to be collected and maintained by the PPA will follow the following management plan:

- **Pairtree data.** About 10G of data sent to the PPA by the HathiTrust containing full-text and metadata information for the 5,000+ items in the PPA. These are currently stored on the CDH servers, but we will request NFS storage from OIT for this content. PPA team members do not need access to these files, however we will need to have an external drive that allows visiting scholars to access the raw data.
- **Solr instance.** This will be generated when we index the full-text and metadata contained within the pairtree files. It will power the search function hosted on prosody.princeton.edu. This instance will be regenerated if we run into a problem (rather than backed up).
- **Software.** Code for the site will be stored on the PPA's GitHub.
- **Design documents.** To be stored on the PPA's Google Drive.
- **Administrative reports.** The PPA project manager will need to access administrative information on site usage and Archive analytics. This will be stored on the PPA's Google Drive.
- **Project documentation.** Write-ups of the PPA's data structure will also be stored on the project's GitHub.

14. Post-grant plans for project

Post-grant plans include partnering with programmers and digital humanists (such as the HathiTrust Research Center) to run advanced textual analysis on the Archive and integrating

text analysis and advanced visualizations on the website. It also includes adding more works to the Archive (see Addendum).

15. Any other issues

This will be the last year for Meagan Wilson to serve as project manager and content editor for the PPA. However, she will begin co-managing and training the new PPA project manager, Mary Naydan, in 2018 to ensure a smooth transition.

Part II: Design Plan

The PPA web application will be implemented in the Python programming language using the Django web framework. The application will take advantage of Django's administrative interface to manage the content, with minimal database records to track and manage digitized text content, which will be stored on the file system. Metadata and full-text data for the digitized texts will be indexed in Solr to support robust, fast, and powerful search and browse functionality. In this phase, the system will only include HathiTrust content, but it will be built with an eye towards supporting digitized materials from other sources. Any corrections to digitized content will be stored either in the database or alongside the digitized materials so that HathiTrust content can easily be re-downloaded without losing corrections.

The first phase of development will be to create the minimal database model with basic administrative functionality, along with a corresponding Solr schema and an automated, repeatable mechanism for indexing digitized content. The schema will be structured so that book metadata and page text content can be searched, grouped, and filtered meaningfully in a single search interface. The first phase of implementation will target bulk import of full-volume materials only. Later phases will add support for adding single items or small batches using the HathiTrust API and support for excerpted materials within a volume. For this project, we will use a Python Solr client to directly manage Solr indexing and querying.¹

Once the Solr schema and indexing mechanism is stable, other features can be built out, including: public-facing search and browse functionality; additional administrative functionality; reporting features. These features can be grouped into releases and ordered according to the preferences and priorities of the team, as there is very little in the way of dependencies across these features. At any point after the first phase, the Solr index can be customized and refined to improve the search behavior (e.g., "boosting" more important fields such as title or author to increase relevance, or customizing synonym and stopword lists to be more useful for the materials on the site).

Where possible, the PPA web application will take advantage of HathiTrust APIs and services. The Data API will be used for importing small batches of items and excerpted materials. We may also investigate the HathiTrust Research Center Portal (HTRC) as a mechanism for PPA users to analyze a subset of the materials on the site, e.g. by selecting items and generating a file that can be used to upload to HTRC to create a workset. As very little in the PPA web

¹ In contrast to other CDH database projects, we will not make use of django-haystack for Solr integration, since the content to be indexed is not contained entirely in the database.

application functionality will be specifically tied to the poetry and prosody materials, the system will be built with generalization in mind, with the goal of enabling other scholars to create similar content-specific digitized text collections.

The baseline features identified as the minimum success criteria will be implemented first. Order of implementation will be based on project team priorities once the initial system is established.

Baseline features (Minimum Viable Product)

Public-facing functionality

- Search and browse digitized works (includes both full volumes and excerpts)
 - Search by keywords anywhere in metadata or full text
 - Filter results by admin-managed collections (e.g. Brogan, typographically unique, poetry, history, grammar, speech)
 - Filter results by publication year range
 - Sort results by relevance, chronology (reversible), alpha by title, alpha by author
 - Display one or two text snippets with keyword matches from the full text for each digitized work
 - Simple search result visualization, e.g. timeline of works by year published
- View individual digitized work
 - Display basic metadata including link to item on HathiTrust
 - Page image thumbnail and text snippets with keyword matches when accessed from a keyword search
- Export bibliographic data to Zotero from search/browse listing or individual page
- Browse by category/collection
 - View a list of PPA administrator-defined and curated collections
 - Collections are displayed with admin-supplied descriptive text and brief summary statistics about the items in that collection (i.e., number of digitized works, date range)
 - Click through from collection to filtered digitized work browse list
- Browse and view content pages and blog posts
- Responsive design for view on desktop, tablet, and mobile (emphasis on desktop/tablet views, but aiming for site content at least to be readable on mobile)

Administrative functionality

- Account management
 - Login with Princeton CAS, manage user accounts, groups, & permissions
- Content management
 - Add/edit content pages
 - Manage site navigation
 - Add/edit blog posts
- Manage digitized works
 - Add new items from HathiTrust (single item or small batch)
 - Add excerpted items
 - Remove items

- Correct basic item-level metadata errors
- Basic reporting functionality (CSV export of all works with user-selected metadata fields)
- Manage collections of digitized works
 - Add/edit collections, including collection description with basic formatting
 - Associate digitized works with one or more collections
 - Bulk search and select digitized works for adding to to collections

After the baseline features have been implemented and deployed to production, enhanced features will be added based on project team priorities and development team schedule allows. The list here is not restrictive or final, but is provided to give some idea of possible directions.

Enhanced features

- Refinements to digitized works list
 - Option to group different printings or editions of the same work (defaults to off)
 - Filter results by publication region, by source type (article, chapter, monograph)
- Refinements to search (e.g. keywords in title or author only, combining multiple search fields)
- Additional visualizations, e.g.:
 - Venn diagram of collections to show relative size and overlap (possibly clickable as another way to browse digitized works by collection)
- Integrate textual analysis tools, e.g. Bookworm
- Export search results in a format that will allow users to create a workset on the HathiTrust Research Center Portal

As with other CDH projects, the application will incorporate Mezzanine, a Django content management tool, to provide project team members with the capability to add and edit site content using the administrative interface. This will make it possible for analytical, narrative, and scholarly material to be published and maintained on the site without requiring additional development time or technical expertise.

The website will be deployed and tested on a CDH virtual machine using the same operating system and infrastructure that will be used for production (RedHat Springdale image). The deploy process will be scripted so that updates can be made automatically and consistently. The production website will be deployed to an OIT virtual machine, and will use the existing CDH MySQL database server for Django user management and site content. Research Computing will provide basic systems administration for virtual machines. Solr will either be deployed on the same virtual machine as the website, or created as one core within a multicore Solr instance on another virtual machine for consolidation with other projects using Solr.

Because there is an existing PPA website (<http://prosody.princeton.edu/>) and the two versions will both public during the usability testing on the new site, we will determine a secondary hostname for one of the sites as well as a switch-over date. If the project team determines it is

appropriate, we will add redirects from urls on the old site to the new version so that the content will be found by any user or search engine referencing the old urls.

See Appendix for site map.

Part III: Work Plan

Gather preliminary article/volume addition information (9/17)

- Work through 125 test cases for non-Hathi additions, find locations, report to RK (MM)

Design test plan for beta-site (8/17 to 12/17)

- Gather preliminary user research (8/17 to 10/17)
 - Identify key user groups, i.e. classroom undergrad, research scholar (MW, MM)
 - Create 1-1 user interview discussion guide in consultation with OIT (MW, XL)
 - Invite 3-5 users to learn about needs and barriers (MW, MM)
 - Hold 1-1 user research sessions (MW, XL)
- Discuss wireframes with same user research participants (10/17 to 11/17)
 - Use in-progress wireframes to conduct interviews (MW, XL)
 - Report back findings to team (MW)
- Create beta-site user testing exercises (10/17 to 12/17)
 - Design specific exercises for users to perform in 1-1 sessions (MW, MM)
 - Create interactive prototype with design mockups in InVision for testing if beta site is not up (XL)

Develop beta-site (9/17 to 1/18)

- Produce site flow (9/17)
 - Translate desired functionalities into site flow (XL)
 - Meet to review the site flow (could be a remote meeting) (XL, MW, MM)
- Design and implement database (10/17)
 - Design and review Solr schema (RK)
 - Develop import scripts (RK)
 - Run initial data import (RK)
- Develop preliminary admin interface: October - November 2017
 - Provide admin user stories to development team (MW, MM)
 - Develop admin interface (RK)
 - Acceptance testing on admin interface (MW, MM)
 - Release to production [temporary url: ppa.princeton.edu] (RK)
- Develop additional features (*see Design Plan*) (10/17 to 12/17)
 - Provide feedback on preliminary admin interface (MW, MM)
 - First-round user stories for baseline features (MW, MM)
 - Develop first round of baseline features (RK)
 - Acceptance test first round of baseline features (MW, MM)
 - Iterative rounds of feature development (RK, MW, MM)
- Produce site wireframes (10/17)
 - Sample site content and detailed user scenarios to Xinyi (MW, MM)
 - First draft of wireframes (XL)

- Meeting to go over wireframes (team)
- Wireframes revised with feedback from meeting (XL)
- Virtual feedback on revised wireframes (MW, MM)
- Produce final site wireframes (XL)
- Determine art direction and visual design (11/17)
 - Meet to go over initial thoughts on art direction and visual identity (MW, MM, XL)
 - Draft visual elements (XL)
 - Provide virtual feedback on drafts (MW, MM)
 - Produce revised drafts and style guides (XL)
 - Meet to go over design mockups (team)
 - Produce final version of visual elements (XL)

BETA SITE LAUNCH! (1/18)

- Swap prosody.princeton.edu from old to new beta-site and host old site at ppa.princeton.edu (RK)
- Add rewrite rules from old site urls to new site urls (RK)
- Publicize new site at MLA (MW, MM)

Run usability testing on beta-site (1/18 to 2/18)

- Select 5 testers from the Bain Swiggett Committee, Historical Poetics Group, and Poetry Graduate Colloquium to test site 1-1 (MW, MN, MM)
- Create record and report feedback (in person or virtually) to RK and XL (MW, MN)

Enhance site functionality and user experience (2/18 to 4/18)

- Prioritize changes based on tester feedback and desired enhanced functionality (team)
- Implement desired changes (RK, XL)
- Consult with visualization developers such as Ben Schmidt from Bookworm (team)

Document site and build repository of Archive for visiting scholars (1/18 to 3/18)

- Write-up of site architecture on GitHub (RK)
- Document detailed workflow and instructions for PPA staff to follow when adding new works to the Archive (RK)
- Review documentation (MM, MW, RK)
- Create a questionnaire for visiting scholars (MW, MN)
- Create a repository for visiting scholars who want to analyze the Archive (RK)
- Document how to access this repository for PPA staff to follow and instruct (RK)
- Test process of using repository to ensure directions work (MM, MW)

Create princeton publicity (3/18)

- Design posters to advertise PPA launch across campus (XL)
- Strategically place posters across campus (MW, MN)
- Create CDH blog post to publicize (MW, MN, XL)

Celebrate PPA completion with CDH advocates at PU (4/18 to 5/18)

- Invite University facilitators who were instrumental to the creation of CDH (Christopher L. Eisgruber, Lynn Shostack, etc.) (MW, MN)
- Plan CDH reception with Sarah Meadows (MW, MN)

Host PPA Advisory Board to test site (4/18 to 5/18)

- Bring Advisory Board to the CDH to test new site (MW, MN)

- Enlist planning help from Sarah Meadows (MW, MN)
- Design testing activities tailored for Board (MW, MN)
- Ask for feedback, technical and editorial (MM, MW, MN)

Launch and publicize completed PPA (6/18 to 8/18)

- Document and share Board feedback, including possible future features (MW, MN)
- Implement desired, possible changes (RK, XL)
- Submit to NINES for peer review (MM, MN)
- Publicize site through appropriate online channels (MM, MN)
- Submit press release announcements to major scholarly organizations (MM, MN)

Project wrap-up with CDH (7/18 to 8/18)

- Write and submit summary of accomplishments (MN, MM)
- Updates to project page (MN, MM)
- Document code (RK)
- MW hand over all past files to MN

Part IV: Budget

[Budget available upon request.]

Part V: Agreement

This document commits the PI and the CDH to the terms elaborated above and reflects mutual agreement regarding the necessary deliverables, responsibilities, and timeline for project success.

Rights, Permissions, and Attribution

We will license under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). As an open source project, will license the code under Apache 2.0. We will fill out an invention disclosure form in order to gain approval from the Office of Technology Licensing in order to release the code. Before approval is granted, the code will be owned by the Trustees of Princeton University.

Web Presence and Project Publicity

The PI will create a publicity page on the CDH website, keeping it up-to-date and accurate during the grant year. The Project Manager will submit at least one blog posts per semester, to be published on the CDH website. The schedule for publishing blog posts is set by the CDH at the beginning of each semester.

Credit

All team members will be credited on the project's website and CDH publicity page. The project's website will include a sponsorship statement (indicating the CDH as well as any other supporting groups, departments, agencies) and will include a citation statement indicating how the project assets should be cited.

Project PI

CDH Associate Director

Date:

Appendix: Site Map

PPA Website Site Map 001
Last update 8/14/2017
Xinyi Li

Addendum: Future Plans for the Archive

The PPA will continue to build the Archive by incorporating new works. When possible, we will find these works in the Hathitrust Digital Library, but when these materials are not available, we predict trying to partner with another aggregator to deliver full-text and metadata. One potential avenue would be ProQuest. We like the idea of partnering with them because their library contains pre-excerpted journal articles (whereas HathiTrust Digital Library does not separate articles from journals). This would be an especially promising partnership because most of the works missing from the PPA are journal articles. In the case that we cannot find/partner with other digitizers, we would like to include editorial bibliographies with WorldCat, ProQuest, and/or other resource links so that users can find their closest copy of the missing PPA material (analog or digital).

A major impetus for the PPA is the ability to trace citation networks and follow the transmission of ideas amongst prosody scholars across time. In addition to adding visualization and text analytics tools for search results, we would like to incorporate a tool similar to Google Scholar allowing users to connect which authors were citing other prododisists.